

Figure 7.2: Updated ExistingCapacity.csv.

Below is the reduced /technodata/power/technodata.csv file, showing the new windturbine in R2. For this, we highlight only the elements we changed from the rows in R1. The rest of the elements are the same for R1 as they are for R2.

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	S	T	U	V
ProcessName	RegionName	Time	Level	cap_par	cap_exp	fix_par	fix_exp	Type	Fuel	EndUse	Agent2
Unit	-	Year	-	MUS\$2010/t-	MUS\$2010/t-	MUS\$2010/t-	MUS\$2010/t-	-	-	-	Retrofit
gasCCGT	R1	2020	fixed	23.782344	1	0	1	energy	gas	electricity	1
windturbine	R1	2020	fixed	36.3077118	1	0	1	energy	wind	electricity	1
gasCCGT	R2	2020	fixed	23.782344	1	0	1	energy	gas	electricity	1
windturbine	R2	2020	fixed	36.3077118	1	0	1	energy	wind	electricity	1

Figure 7.3: Updated Technodata.csv.

Now, go ahead and amend all of the other input files for each of the sectors, the Agents file and the input files BaseYearExport, BaseYearImport and Projections.csv by copying and pasting the rows from R1 and replacing the RegionName with R2 for the new rows. All of the edited input files can be seen at the zenodo link:

<https://zenodo.org/record/6327789#.Yil1ri-l1pQ>

Again, we will run the results using the python -m pip muse settings.toml in anaconda prompt, and analyse the data using excel as follows:

Figure 7.4: Capacity visualisation for both regions in the power sector - a) Region = R1, b) Region = R2.

Summary

In this hands-on we added a new fictional region with the same characteristics for both of these regions. We see that the output of the two regions in the power sector are the same. This is because the characteristics in both regions are identical.